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there's
something
science
can do.

Policy Brief 2025/003
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By Dylan Lamberti

US trade policy to fight foreign drug caps

Issue/problem

On March 21, 2025 the American First Policy Institute (AFPI) released a policy brief titled "[Put Americans First by Ending Global Freeloading](#)," arguing that US consumers disproportionately pay for the costs of innovation and research and development.

Description of the problem

AFPI was [founded in 2021](#) by now-Agriculture Secretary Brooke Rollins, now-Education Secretary Linda McMahon and Larry Kudlow, the former Director of the National Economic Council during Trump's first term. The AFPI has a strong policy influence within the second Trump administration, including in respect of the dismantlement of the [Department of Education](#).

The brief argues that countries outside the US pay only 24% of research and development which it claims is unfair to US consumers.

Results

The brief proposes several solutions to the problem of high drug prices including implementing 'Most Favoured Nation' pricing into Medicare and Medicaid, banning companies that charge lower international prices from accessing Medicare and Medicaid, and making the issue of drug supply a bargaining chip in trade negotiations. All proposed solutions carry the risk of higher prices and reduced access to American pharmaceutical products.

Lessons learned

This policy debate is not new. In 2018, the Trump administration proposed the [International Pricing Index](#) model, which sought to align certain U.S. drug prices with those in other high income nations. The AFPI's proposal represents a shift back toward leveraging trade policy to address the issue and integrates with the current administration's strong messaging on renegotiating international trade agreements because of unfair effects on the American economy.

The pharmaceutical industry has shown its willingness to engage on those terms. A day before the AFPI's paper was released, Pharmaceutical Research and Manufacturers of America [filed a complaint](#) with the US government and called for reciprocal tariffs to be levied against Australia over its Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme, claiming that the process '[systematically devalues US medicine](#)'.